

ACTIVITY LEVELS

TABLE 1: Activity levels (h:mm:ss) in selected Slack and Gitter rooms

Room name (G (Gitter) or S (Slack))	Avg (median) activity level	Number of participants
Reaction commerce (G)	1:06:14 (0:01:39)	708
Scala on Android (G)	2:09:00 (0:01:25)	98
Ethereum (G)	0:25:49 (0:01:07)	2021
HelpJavaScript (G)	0:01:01 (0:00:17)	28246
Monogame (G)	1:32:18 (0:01:09)	218
Mithriljs (G)	0:15:00 (0:01:02)	742
Angular (G)	0:02:48 (0:00:33)	7820
Semantic Org (G)	1:23:15 (0:04:17)	1559
Sschmid Entitas CSharp (G)	1:40:33 (0:02:14)	282
Dotnet Orleans (G)	0:18:04 (0:01:03)	455
Cordova (S)	1:07:55 (0:02:38)	270
Clojure (S)	0:13:42 (0:01:25)	711